

EFFECTS OF CAREER GUIDANCE AND CAREER COUNSELLING TECHNIQUES ON STUDENTS VOCATIONAL MATURITY

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Abstract:

This study investigated the effects of career guidance method and career counselling method on student's vocational maturity. The main purpose of the study is to find out which of the two purposed techniques will best facilitate the development of vocational maturity among secondary school adolescents in Ekiti State, Nigeria. Two research questions were raised to guide the study and one hypothesis was formulated. The study was a quasi-experimental design of pre-test and post-test two experimental groups. The instrument used was an adopted inventory used by Kuti in 1979. The inventory was named Career Development Inventory (CDI). The validation of the instrument was re-established with reliability co-efficient of 74, 76 and 80 respectively in the sub-scale A, B, C. Treatments were done in two different schools. Career Guidance Technique (CGT) was used in school A, while, Career Counselling Technique (CCT) was used in school B, Career Development Inventory (CDI) was used as measure of vocational maturity at pre-test and post-test. Based on data collected and analysed, the results revealed general improvement in the students' vocational maturity after treatment. The study also revealed that Career Counselling Technique (CCT) improve vocational maturity better than Career Guidance Technique (CGT). But both (CCT) and (CGT) help in the improvement of vocational maturity of students. Vocational or career guidance and counselling programme should be made compulsory in all secondary schools in Ekiti State.

Keywords: career guidance technique (CGT), career counselling technique (CCT), vocational maturity, career development inventory (CDI)

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1. Introduction

The organisation of career guidance services in a school system as a pioneer demands considerable tact and skills. Many laudable ideas and programmes have failed because the starting off or wrong steps. Success of any enterprise within the school system calls for the co-operation all and sundry in the system. Good programmes fail to be effective when the spirit of co-operation and teamwork are lacking among the operators. Methods, strategies and techniques of initiating guidance programme are bound to vary to accommodate the varying conditions in different schools or communities (Makinde & Alao, 1987). For any guidance services or programme to achieve its goals, a guidance package should be provided as a service that will enhance the student maturity within the school guidance programme.

Prominent among the school guidance programme is career education, career education is more than a matter of helping students to find jobs but include organising a career programme in the schools among the students in the senior secondary level to equip these students on understanding toward self-knowledge and the world of work. Ipaye (1983) stressed that career education should enable students understand and evaluate their society as a work organisation and assess their own chances and place as individual within that work organisation. Students therefore needed information through a career guidance and counselling programme with the use of an effective guidance and counselling techniques to gain some knowledge and understanding of the purposes and conditions of work even while at school.

To decide on a suitable or right career, the individual should know himself, and the occupations that are available. For better self-understanding, interest, aptitude, temperament and educational attainment should be properly addressed. Evidence abounds in literature that the 'self' or individual's view of self (self-knowledge) is the most important component of human personality. Reports of some researchers have identified low self-knowledge as one of the most important factors responsible for poor career decision making among Nigerian adolescents (Okatahi and Adeyanju (1989), Kutara (1995) Okon (2001). Self-knowledge has been described as the awareness of individual of his/her self and one's own ability. Owuamanam (2003) states that self-concept is a sum total of all the characteristics a person attribute to himself both the positive and negative values he attaches to the characteristics. By the observations above, self-concept or self-knowledge is view as the individual evaluation of himself in term of the totality of his abilities, attitudes, qualities, personalities, perceptions, judgement, values and capabilities.

Expectations of individual at times influence the planning and performance of such an individual toward career decision making. Famade (2001) observes that expectations of teachers and the school counsellors on their students greatly influence their planning. Counsellors positive expectations of their students always call for guidance programmes that was designed and presented as a school guidance programme with the co-operation of other significant others in the school setting for better students decision making. Tamunomama (1996) in Gbore (2006) list four attributes of self-concept as academic self-concept, physical self-concept, psychological self-concept and social self-concept as attributes considered for decision making in the world of work. The techniques used in this study for improving vocational maturity of secondary school students is the career guidance approach to vocational development.

Some researchers had shed light on the relative effectiveness of the methods, some studies reported that the career guidance approach is more effective than career counselling approach, while some are of the opinion that career counselling technique was better. For clarity and avoidance of doubt, this study was put in place and was carried out in Ekiti State of Nigeria.

Fisher (1980) attempted to measure the relative effectiveness of career guidance programme on a measure of career maturity for Roman Catholic High School students in one of his studies on vocational development in United States of America. The treatment used was a three session programme in vocational guidance and it consist of lectures, the use of visual aids, administration of an interest inventory and inventory of work related activities. The dependent variable for the study was career maturity as measured by scores obtained on the career maturity inventory. The result revealed no significant difference on the level of career maturity between the treatment and control group. Brown and Book (1991) finding disagree with the findings of Fisher (1980) Broom and Book, argued that their won experiment difference was found between the treated and control group.

In a longitudinal study of Amundson, Borgen and Tench (2004), they found that young people left high school unprepared for current career realities and both the career and personal areas of adolescents lives were in a state of change and uncertainty. This holds the opinion that toward the end of student's final year in secondary school, they expressed optimism entering the career area of their choice and are expected to be successful workers. About half of the subjects used in their study indicated some concern about meeting post – secondary entrance standards. Through observations, some months following graduation from secondary school, depression, self-esteem, and anxiety were correlated with a range of perceived problems which includes lack of money lack of support from parents and friends external attributes of

career/employment difficulties. The focus of this study for the guidance practitioners in Nigerian secondary schools is to provide career guidance and career counselling programmes for students to foster vocational maturity. The programme is to assist Nigerian students in arriving at wise decision on occupational options in their later days. Secondary school education should help in preparing students for career decision making if unable to proceed to higher level of education.

2. Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to determine the effects of career guidance and career counselling techniques on the vocational maturity of secondary school students in Nigeria. Specifically the programme was meant to find out which of career guidance and career counselling technique will be effective in enhancing the vocational development of Nigerian adolescents.

2.1 Research Questions

One general question was raised to guide the study base on the general questions raised, one research question was also postulated:

1. What is the level of students' vocational maturity?
2. Will career guidance techniques (CGT) and career counselling technique (CCT) improve the student's vocational maturity?

2.2 Research Hypothesis

Based on the research question raised, one hypothesis was formulated.

1. There is no significant difference between the vocational maturity of students exposed to career guidance techniques (CGT) and career counselling technique (CCT).

3. Methodology

The study was a quasi-experimental design of pre-test and post-test two experimental groups as represented below:

Q₁ X₁ O₂
O₃ X₂ Q

Where O₁

O₃ are pre-tests

O₂ O₄ are post-tests

X₁ are group with Guidance Technique (Treatment)

X₂ are group with Counselling Technique (Treatment)

The population for the study was all the secondary school students in senior secondary school class II in Nigeria. The sample of the study consisted of 240 students of 120 male and 120 female selected from four secondary schools in two local government area of Ekiti State using stratified, simple random sampling and purposive techniques. The selection of the local government areas was done randomly, while the strata recognised the sex and location of schools, purposive recognised the student's selection and the state.

There are two experimental groups for the study with 120 students in each groups. The protest of the instrument was administered on all the students in their various schools. For thus study, students that score 81 to 323 were regarded as been matured vocationally. Which those students that scored from 80 – 58 were tagged to be students with low vocational maturity. To avoid interference during treatments, subjects, were attended to in their various schools, they were pre-tested, Treated and post-tested, than data were gathered for analysis.

3.1 Research Instrument

The instrument for data collection was an adapted Career Development Inventory (CDI) from Kuti (1979). This inventory had been used in Nigeria by Kuti. He stated that the modified instruments differs from the original, not interim of format or construct, but in term of eliminated items. The eliminated items were substituted with equivalent English words that are familiarly known and commonly used and understood by literate Nigerians. CDI is an objective multifactor, self-administering inventory design to measure the vocational maturity of males and females adolescents. The instrument is of three scales, the first two scales measure attitudinal components while the third scale measures the cognitive components of vocational maturity of respondents. The first and second parts of the scales consisted of items which are indicative of planning orientation, and the use of resources for exploration of information. The response continuum is on a five points (a b c d e) interpreted to mean (1 2 3 4 5) respectively. The range of scores in the two parts is from 55 - 58 - 290. The third scale which is the third part of the instrument comprises occupational information and knowledge of the world of work. The response to each item is also in five point (a b c d e) but only one of the options is the correct answer and the score is 1. The range of score in this part is 0 - 35. Therefore, the range of score for the whole scale, that is, the first, second and the third part of the scale is 58 - 323. Subjects that score below 25% of the total scores are regarded as vocationally immature.

3.2 Validity of the Instrument

The face and construct validity of the sub-scale A B C of the CDI has been established by Kuti (1979). He reported the validity co-efficient of the sub-scale as 0.75, 0.62 and 0.69 respectively. However, since the instrument was adapted for this present study, the face and construct validity was re-established by test experts where some items were amended, some were modified to reflect the students understanding in Ekiti State. The establishment of the instrument reliability was also done by Kuti with the reliability co-efficient of 0.78, 0.80 and 0.75 respectively. The reliability co-efficient instrument was also re-confirmed to give 0.72, 0.74 and 0.80 respectively.

3.2 Experimental Procedure

The treatment package developed and used in this study was tagged “Group career guidance and counselling programme”. In the schools used, the school counsellor of each schools work co-operatively with the researcher with the help of the school counsellors the principal, staff and all the students also work with the research with their full co-operation.

Group A — Career Guidance Technique (CGT) in the school where CGT was used, with the help of the school counsellor, five guidance sessions was agreed on.

- 1st session: Pre-test, the Career Development Inventory (CDI) was administered on the students and collected back.
- 2nd session: Treatment starts with organisation of career talk by professionals.
- 3rd session: Treatment continue with career talk by professional different from the 2nd session.
- 4th session: Researcher and school counsellor interactions with the student as a follow-up responses to their previous interactions with professionals.
- 5th session: Administration of post-test on the students that complete sessions.

Group B — Career Counselling Technique (CCT) as applicable in the group A school, co-operation of all the staff and students was secured, the school counsellor also work co-operatively with the researcher. Five counselling sessions was arrived at:

- 1st session: Pre-test, students were asked to complete the CDI and collected back.
- 2nd session: Treatment started by asking the students to complete the Vocational Interest Inventory (VII) of Bakare. Here the students respond were scored and the interest profile of each students were drawn.
- 3rd session: Treatment continue, occupation clusters were identified as outdoor, mechanical, computational, scientific, persuasive, artistic, literary musical, social services and clerical.

- 4th session: All the identified occupational clusters were clearly explained with sample of occupation associated with each cluster. Employment prospects, nature of work, work environment, qualifications, preparations entrance, advancement were well explored with the students.
- 5th session: Administration of post-test on the students that complete all the session.

3.3 Administration of Post-test and Data Analysis

At the end of each experimental session, the Career Development Inventory (CDI) was administered accordingly and data were drawn from the scores for analysis. Descriptive statistics we rued, bar chart was also use, while t-test was used to test the only hypothesis formulated at 0.05 level of significance.

4. Results

The results of the research questions and the hypothesis formulated and tested at 0.05 significance and discussion of findings are presented here.

Question 1: What is the level of students' vocational maturity?

Table 1: Frequency count and percentage of student level of vocational maturity before treatment

Maturity Level	Range of Scores	Frequency	Relative Percentages
High	162 – 323	40	16.7
Moderate	81 – 161	80	33.3
Low	0 – 80	120	50.3
Total		240	100

The table 1 revealed that 40 students representing 16.7% had high vocational maturity, 80 students representing 33.3% had moderate vocational maturity, while 120 students representing 50% had a very low vocational maturity. This results shows that majority of the student had low vocational maturity before treatment.

Table 2: Frequency counts and percentage of student level of vocational maturity after treatment

Maturity Level	Range of Scores	Frequency	Relative Percentages
High	162 – 323	50	20.8
Moderate	81 – 161	90	37.5
Low	0 – 80	100	41.7
Total		240	100

Table 2 revealed that 50 student representing 20.8% had high vocational maturity after treatment, 90 students representing 37.5% had moderate vocational maturity, while 100 students representing 41.7% still maintain their low level after treatment. This result shows that there is improvement in the vocational maturity of students after treatment.

Hypothesis (HO): There is no significant difference between the vocational maturity of students exposed to group career guidance (CGT) and (CCT) techniques.

Table 3: t-test comparison of vocational maturity of students exposed to CGT and CCT techniques

Groups	N	mean	SD	df	t-cal	t-tab
CGT	72	90.54	16.47	134	8.097	1.96
CCT	64	127.89	34.76			

P < 0.05 (Significant)

Table 3 revealed that the mean scores of CGT and CCT are 90.54 and 127.89 respectively, while the t-calculated is 8.097 and it is greater than the table value of 1.96. This implies that there is significant difference between the vocational maturity of students exposed to CGT and CCT. This implies that CCT improved the vocational maturity of students better than CGT.

5. Discussion, Conclusion and Recommendation

The results of the study revealed a general low vocational maturity of the respondents before treatment. This implies that majority of the participants scores were below the high and moderately vocationally matured level. The findings clearly showed that many students in Ekiti State secondary schools were not exposed to vocational education as expected from the school counsellor. This finding is in line with the observation of Vernon (2006), that many adolescent who completed secondary school to join the workforce are not fulfilled in their expectations and aspirations concerning career development. Meanwhile, according to Vernon, termination of education is not a

crime but students should be helped to reach a level of self-understanding and self-fulfillment concerning career expectations.

This study also revealed that the group guidance and counselling programme package brought about improvement in the students vocational maturity. This finding tends to establish the fact that if students are exposed to training in vocational education, their vocational behaviour will improve. The students will also have better orientation toward career choice and what information or exploration to make in respect of career planning. The finding revealed percentage increased in all the locations where training took place.

The findings of the study also established the fact that using career guidance technique (CGT) will be of benefit to students in fostering vocational maturity. The study also suggests that the use of career counselling technique (CCT) would lead to better improvement in the vocational education. The results revealed that both techniques improve the student's vocational maturity. This finding agrees with Egbochukwu (1998) on her investigation on the effect of three guidance techniques and initial entry career maturity behaviour on student's self-appraisal. The result of this study negates the general belief that the act of giving vocational education does not need a special training, that performance in school subjects is sufficient to make one understand oneself toward career choice (Adeyemo, 2005).

Conclusively, the study revealed that group career guidance and counselling techniques led to improvement in vocational maturity of students. Any of the guidance and counselling technique helps in improving vocational maturity.

Vocational or career counselling should be made compulsory in all secondary schools in Ekiti State. School authority should support their school counsellors to incorporate into school programmes and curriculum the vocational education.

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